

**A STUDY ON SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY ON KARNATAKA COTTON INDUSTRY
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ABSTRACT

This study examines social responsibility within the Karnataka cotton industry, focusing on the Afzalpur region. The cotton sector plays a vital role in the local economy, providing livelihoods for thousands of farmers and workers. However, it also faces challenges related to environmental sustainability, labor practices, and community welfare.

Through qualitative and quantitative analyses, the research highlights the industry's impact on local communities, including employment opportunities, income generation, and social development initiatives. The findings indicate that while some cotton producers engage in socially responsible practices—such as fair labor standards and eco-friendly farming techniques—there is a significant gap in widespread adoption across the industry.

The study underscores the importance of stakeholder engagement, including government, NGOs, and corporate entities, in promoting sustainable practices. Recommendations for enhancing corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives include better education for farmers on sustainable methods, improved labor conditions, and investment in local infrastructure.

Ultimately, fostering social responsibility in the Karnataka cotton industry can lead to more sustainable economic growth, improved community well-being, and a healthier environment, positioning Afzalpur as a model for responsible agricultural practices.

Keywords:

Corporate social responsibility, cotton industry, eco-friendly, investment

INTRODUCTION ABOUT THE ORGANISATION STUDY

The cotton industry in India has a rich history dating back to 19th century, when the 'British East India Company established' several beneficial industries and the country began to embrace a new era of mechanization. Cotton was a staple fabric that necessary almost every aspect of Indian life at work.

The Indian Cotton Industry was the specific sector that attracted emerging Indian industries from its modest beginnings. James Landon established the Broach Cotton Mill in 1854 with the goal of realizing that ideal. After the first was successful in 1856, 79 cotton mills were up and running by 1883, when Bombay took the lead in the industrial sector. Thus, the founding of the cotton industry marked the beginning of new era in history. In Bengal, the first automated sawmill was established in 1855. The Indian government issued a waste lands Oder in October 1861 to promote the growing of cotton.

"In 1862, Hugh Mason, the chairman of the Manchester Cotton Company's board, attempted to remove Sir Charles Wood (1800–1885), the secretary of state for Indian affairs." Mason believed that the Indian Government was maintaining more marketable in Indian. 64 just mill existed in Bengal, with 36000 looms employing a total of 225000 workers in 1913.

One of India's main crops and the main source of raw-materials for the country's textile industry is cotton. In addition to providing the Indian people with the needs of life, the cotton sector is crucial to the nation's industrial production, job creation, and export revenue. It makes up around 14.42% of the nation's export revenue, 4% of the GDP, and 14% of industrial production. India is the only nation that cultivates Gossiper arboretum and herbaceous (Asian cotton), G. barb dense (Egyptian cotton), and G. hirsute—the four varieties of cultivated cotton. 90% of te hybrid is made up

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of Gossipier hirsute '(American Upland cotton)'. G. hirsute is the species used in all modern BT cotton hybrids and cotton grown in India.

Three regions of the nation are used to produce cotton in India: the northern region, which includes the states of 'Punjab', 'Haryana', and 'Rajasthan'; the central region, which includes states of 'Maharashtra', 'Madhya Pradesh', and 'Gujarat'; and the southern region, which includes the states of 'Andhra Pradesh', 'Karnataka', and 'Tamil Nadu'. In addition to the eastern State of Odisha, there are nine other States where cotton production has become more popular. During the 2008–09 cotton season, the nation produced 4.93 million metric tons of cotton, or 29.0 million bales kegs each, marking the sixth straight year, of greater cotton harvests. Cotton output has increased over the past few decades, rising from 7.5 million bales in 1983–1984 to 16.3 million bales weighing 170 kg each in 1998–1999.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In this era of modernity, the majority of textile mills worldwide and in India are calling for more subjective cotton, as is the majority of texture producing facilities worldwide and in India. Therefore, Ginning Pressing Industries' modernization should provide cotton for demand development to be used. There area, a lot of flaws with traditional technologies nowadays. Cotton fines might be reduced. Because integration may have, more benefits than dissection, Indian cotton's effects on the whole market may not be favourable. As a result, modernization of the country's ginning pressing industries is necessary. The previous Act's arrangements were designed to define "managers" and "staff" for businesses, that have been biased to govern and oversee the group of workers belonging to the specific representatives in question. This includes management agreements, whether verbal or written, with an emphasis on workplace security. The action prohibits resolute hindrance by representatives and/or substance abuse, comforts, or multiple articles outfitted within the assembly office with regard to wellbeing, security, and government assistance performed effectively there. Furthermore, the deliberate display and never, at this point, with the intention that it will undoubtedly be dangerous for her or anybody else. Additionally, workers haphazardly fail to use gadgets or other apparatuses that ensure safety and well-being.

1. **'YAKSHEV (1991)'** In his article titled "A Novel Approach to the Provision of Social Security in the USSR," he concentrated on the idea that friendly assurance played a vital social and economic role the "USSR". In addition computer to the outcome of stage inside framework, it appears that not only trust boost creation enough to ensure better association isn't least difficult to increase amount of social wellbeing anyway for impoverished folks in am order to improve the convenience of social insurance policy. In order, to get more ecologically friendly distribution of alternatives, it is imperative to eliminate the general negative correlation between consumption and money, and to find the highest degree of correspondence between the attributes derived from specific
2. **'SUBRAMANIAN (1994)'** describes how the government kept retirement as a confidence by using the entire society for every person, to maintain a reputation for staying or, in the absence of anything better, a good in vogue regarding staying, via reward dispersal, primarily based on country wide fortitude. In a few steps, the possibility of the federal retirement guide that it would point out should be determined in order to arrange for the neighbourhood to provide assistance to the local areas where you can achieve a decent standard of living, and to keep an eye on these people to prevent them from falling as a result of any possibility.
3. **'GUHAN (1994)'** According to article "Government-backed Retirement Choices for Developing Countries," one of main reasons why the discussion of friendly guarantee in developing countries began in the 1980s is that industry and developing nations tend to use the term "interpersonal security accessibility" more frequently than other countries. Another issue is that while the portfolio recognizes actions to alleviate destitution immediately, it cannot be counted on to guarantee security. This is because measures to prepare for or ensure that the impoverished state of not having will be perceived are taken, and it is repeatedly acknowledged that interpersonal wellbeing nets can assist the adverse during the period of change that starts in agricultural countries within the country.

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4. **'BENEDICT MARY ELLEN and SHAW KATHRYN (1995)'** highlight the use of suggested metrics for income inequality and particular pension gain information for participants in the Consumer Financing Survey from 1983, highlighting the significant impact that monthly pension benefits have on the income distribution under investigation. According to the impact, the personal pension income disparity is only rising by about 2% for most working people each year, but it is 21% for men and women in unions. Additionally, the analysis demonstrates that private pensions increase monthly income in an equitable manner in majority of cases by lowering the cost of returning to work, most likely through the use of "retirement pensions" and an increase in pensions with age. Personal pension contributions will not impact the predicted lifetime distribution going forward.
5. **'GROVER CHRIS (2003)'** identifies the goal of any new labor force participation and health reform software as being to rebuild the labor force in order to fulfill its role in maintaining economic stability. Allowing the most cost-effective labor to be used properly for financial gain through a distribution of direct and indirect earnings subsidies is crucial, as is requiring more advanced businesses to be competitive for paid art.
6. **'SUSANA LOEB, ET. AL. (2003)'** said that the lives of younger people would typically change at the same time that welfare job reform can improve women's efforts industry involvement. This awareness was created in a novel randomized challenge experiment conducted in Connecticut to investigate the potential relationship between mother employment ranges and software usage and changes in early formative years education and cognitive development. Children of mothers who signed Connecticut's first venture have a project with a 21-week time restriction and job bonuses, illustrating the benefits of moderate compared to the start of the look at change organization. Numerous capacity factors for this well-known influence have been examined, such as the employment and income of mothers, the specific family environment.
7. **'ROBERT STRATHDEE (2004)'** centered on the plan attempt in New Zealand and provides a record of interviews to ascertain the specific influence of "outsourcing" the tutors who work with the specific youth as well as the jobless. Hiring an impartial company to deliver services, or outsourcing procedures as it is more colloquially known, has become a common practice in business and plays a significant role in social coverage in many western countries throughout the globe. She stated that outsourcing is utilized to control almost all of the people that work with jobless human beings in New Zealand. The data illustrates how outsourcing improves this particular manage by creating uncertainty in the tutoring industry. In this area, outsourcing authorizations result in a regulatory.
8. 14. Teachers are attempting to increase student labor in order to simplify employment through construction.
9. **'JORGE SOARES (2005)'** has researched the bias of effective methods to ascertain the haven effect of social safety systems regarding certain decisions, and as a consequence, rate factors have an impact on labor income and cost savings. While social security should provide threat protection, it may also force debt upon men and Less affluent women compared to those who would most benefit from, the most fulfilling path of absorption. The outcome shows that fair acts can significantly investigate the influence regarding the man or woman, regardless of these attributes. He has studied the ways in which the different features of the premium social safety device affect the related prejudice. Social protection generally affects the wellbeing.
10. **'FRANKLIN A. MICHELLO and WILLIAM F FORD (2006)'** Learn about and examine the conflict that arises between the goal of lowering the financial unemployment rate and various U. T. social safety reform initiatives that might help postpone monthly pension decisions. The study shows that U.H. social protection reform initiatives can also effectively raise the financial unemployment rate by utilizing existing market trends in the period composition of the U.S. workforce. This person came to, conclusion efforts to encourage senior citizens might alleviate market pressures even if unemployment stays at the rate of non-accelerating inflation of unemployment.
11. **'ROBERT J LERNKE, ROBERT WITT and ANN DRYDEN WITTE (2007)'** Examine the ways in which the commercial infant care centers, newborn child vouchers for proper care, and federal government support affect the beneficiaries' progress in receiving government assistance to work. In the remarkable, she wanted to recognize the parameters that drive single parents to quickly exit the workplace and what prompts single parents to look for alternative childcare or after-school programs before venturing into the competitive job market.

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When considering financial do-it-yourself sufficiency, these types of limit alteration method distinctions are crucial. Although the data are often suppressed to prevent particular parents from benefiting from the advancement of public support, they might examine the consequences.

12. **'LEA HENDRICKSON (2008)'** Examine how export companies are reorganized from the perspective of gender inequality in government transportation, and use this information to build a thorough inquiry that fits into the framework of successful operations. Through the use of artwork, standard instructions, and the finished practical attendances, the program of the look-at may help the staff choose in a much more significant socio-social context. The author tends to focus on the unique vulnerability of semible medical attendants who have institutional ties "among" the worker's guild subculture, the bigger plus reduction exercise, and the social and wellness aracs. Sectorial isolation is usually followed by the specific national arrangement period table on function trade, which claims.
13. **'DR. P. VENUGOPAL AND T. BHASKAR (2011)'** discovered that government support operations, such as action, clinical, planning, housing, transportation, sterilization, and assurance, are met with satisfaction by the personnel. Additionally, workers are often free to receive significant government benefits including maternity remittances, work compensation, ESI, illness, and P.F. Even while there is a clear romantic relationship between the organization and its personnel, who may have dreams connected to e commercial endeavor, these types of acts have an influence on the unusual aspects of life.
14. **'Hnagarki (2014)'** discusses the specific relationship between the level of employee entertainment and government assistance programs in selected state banks located in the Hyderabad region of Karnataka. It is evident that working under the guidance of banks while receiving government aid isn't as enjoyable for all of the representatives. to eat in the direction of the customer's front side.'

3. Research design'

'STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM'

The study's claim concerns the welfare of workers in the cotton ginning sector. Since complete automation is impractical for this organization, the production that is done there mostly rests on the productivity of the workers, who are given various facilities to keep them motivated. This research was done to learn more about the many welfare programs the firm offers, to find out what the employees' think of these resources, and to find out if there any details they are not satisfied.

'NEED FOR THE STUDY'

- To comprehend Karnataka Cotton Industry Ltd.'s social responsibility's efficacy.
- To understand the routine operations that occur in a production
- To Consider connecting theoretical ideas to real-world organizational actions.
- To understand the history of the factory
- To increase productivity and the caliber and volume of HR procedures

'SCOPE OF THE STUDY'

The scope of a study on the social responsibility of the cotton-industry involves outlining the specific areas and dimensions that will be investigated. This scope defines the boundaries of the research and identifies the key topics and questions that the study will address. Here's a comprehensive outline of potential scope elements for such a study.

OBJECTIVE

- To know, the Environmental Sustainability in social responsibility at KCI
- To understand the circumstances around worker safety
- To cite KCI's Consumer Awareness and Education Program.
- To ascertain the extent of contentment in social responsibility at KCI
- To deliver, useful tip to enhance social responsibility at KCI
- To control, degree of difficulty that workers and employees'

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“RESERCH METHODOLOGY”

The process for creating new continuous compositions that incorporates factual devices, test designs, vote formats, records agreement, and plan elements is frequently used to examine the data that has been gathered.

‘RESERCH DESIGN’

The study's focus is on descriptions.

‘TYPES OF DATA CAST-OFF FOR THE STUDY’

‘Primary data; and ‘secondary data’ are using for this study’.

‘SOURCES OF DATA’

The main sources of data were structured questionnaires, phone interviews, and emails that were sent directly to the customers.

“Secondary data were gathered from” corporate records, textbooks, and the Internet.

“METHOD OF DATA COLLECTION”

- Data is gathered using the specifics of every KCI department.
- Primary, Following data collection, study was done, and necessary recommendations were made in light of the observations and conclusions.
- Secondary information, was also gathered from textbooks, periodicals, website’s the companies, and magazines.

“SAMPLING DESIGN”

Sampling unit: Cotton ginning industry personnel

Number of samples: Fifty employees’ make up the study's sample size.

“SAMPLING TECHNIQUE”

The Random sampling is the sampling method that will be used in this study.

‘TOOLS FOR PRESENTATION OF DATA’

TablesPie charts are employed in data visualization.

‘VARIABLES USED’

‘Employee welfare measures (Independent Variable)’

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY”

- The Customers' individual sentiments can vary from person, to person.
- All study, is also impacted by the questionnaire's shortcomings.
- This, model could not be regarded as a reliable indicator of the whole population.
- There There's a chance that human mistake occurred.

4. ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

To extract meaningful information from the data and make decisions based on that information is the aim of data analysis. Conversely, data analysis may assist in transforming unprocessed data into meaningful insights, figures, and justifications.

The process of evaluating data in an, order draw a well-informed judgment is referred to as data interpretation. Data interpretation offers meaning to the information analyzed and determines its recommendations and predictions.

My research using the gathered data will be better understood and conclusions drawn thanks to analysis and ‘interpretation’.

Table 4.1

“Displaying the respondents' educational background

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'Response's	No of Respondent's	Percentage(%)
B.com/M.com	24	48%
M B A	06	12%
B A	04	08%
M A	06	12%
B S C	06	12%
M C A	04	08%
Total	50	100%

'Analysis';

According to the above statistics, 68% of workers are graduates, with the remaining 32% being postgraduates.

'INTERPRETATION';

As can be seen from the overhead graph, 24 responders are from B.com/M.com, 04 from BA MCA, 06 from BSC MCA MA, and a very small number, i.e., 06, are from BA MCA.

Table 4.2 Displaying the employee's professional experience

'Responses'	No. of respondents	Percentage
'0-5 years	'33	66%
5-10 years	10	20%
10-15 years	3	06%
'More than 15 years	4	08%
'Total=	50'	'100%

'Analysis';

The aforementioned data indicates that 66% of employees', have less than 5, years' worth of work experience, 20% have five to ten years' worth, 6% have ten to fifteen years' worth, and remaining 8% possess more than fifteen years working experiences.

'INTERPRETATION':

The aforementioned graph displays the employee's job experience inside the company. There are 44 workers who have worked with the company for over 15 years. 33 of them are currently employed for 0-5 years, 10 for 5-10 years,

03 for 10-15 years, and the remaining 10 for more than 15 years.

'Table 4.3 'Presentation the balancing the work life'

'Work life balance'	'No of Respondents'	'Percentage(%)'
Yes	47	94%
No	03	06%
Total	50	'100%

'Analysis';

The table above illustrates how employees' may balance their professional and personal lives. The remaining 6% of employees' are "Responses" as no, whereas the other 94% of employees' are "Responses" as yes.

'INTERPRETATION';

Based on the aforementioned graphs, it is evident that 47 individuals exhibit a healthy work-life balance, while the remaining 03 people are classified as "Responses" because to their non-balanced work-life dynamics within the firm.

'Table 4.4 Presentation working environment of the organisation'

Category	'No of Respondent's'	Percentage(%)
Highly satisfactory	36	72%
Satisfactory	14	28%
Total	50	'100%

'Analysis'

Giving to above table, 72% of workers are "Responses"—that is, they are very satisfied with working settings, while the remaining 28% are "Responses"—that is they are happy with their working environments within the company.

INTERPRETATION;

According to the above graph, fourteen workers are "Responses," meaning they are content with their working conditions at the company, while the remaining thirty-six employees' are "Responses," meaning they are extremely happy with their working settings.

Table 4.5 Showing The respondents' contentment with health benefits

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'Response'	No of Respondent's	Percentage(%)
Highly satisfied	28	56%
Satisfied	22	44%
Total	50	'100%

'Analysis';

The above table displays the 56% of employee "Responses" that express a high level of satisfaction with the medical benefits offered by the organization to them and their families, as well as the 44% of employee "Responses" that express a satisfaction with the medical benefits offered to them and their families by the organizations.

'INTERPRETATION'

The graphs above illustrate the 28 employee "Responses" who expressed a high level of satisfaction with the medical benefits that an, organization offered to them and their families, as well as the 22 other employee "Responses" who expressed a satisfactory level, satisfaction with medical benefits that an, organization offered to them and families.

05. Findings and suggestion

'FINDINGS'

- Giving to the graph, 32% of employees' are post-grads and 68% of employees' are graduates.
- The graph indicates that 66% of employees' have worked for less than five years, 20% h worked for five to ten years, 6% have worked for ten to fifteen years, and 8% have worked for more than fifteen years.
- According to the graph, 94% of workers balance their personal and professional lives, while 6% do not.
- According to the graph, 28% of workers are content with their workplace environment and 72% of workers are extremely happy.
- The graph indicates that 44% of workers are content with the medical benefits that the company offers to its employees' and their families, while 56% of workers are extremely happy.
- The chart illustrates how maternity leave helped the organization 96% of workers indicate that they have a "yes," while 4% indicate that they have a "no."
- According to the graph, 38% of workers are very satisfied. Half of the workforce is extremely content. 12% of workers are extremely dissatisfied with the organization's working hours, compared to 5% who are not happy.
- The graph indicates that 6% of workers are not pleased and 14% are extremely dissatisfied. The organization offers its employees' an overtime allowance; 52% of employees' are happy, and 12% are extremely satisfied.

'SUGGESTIONS'

- More training sessions should be held to promote staff efficiency;
- Recreation facilities should be enhanced to boost employee morale and lower stress levels; The food canteen's quality might be raised.
- Health camps should be held at least once a month to enhance staff counselling and yearly physical examinations.

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- The business ought to offer breakfast services
- Employee quarters should be refurbished, and the company should have enough equipment for, first aid box.
- The researcher discovers that workers are content with the welfare programs offered by KCI.
- Welfare programs are important for employee motivation, which raises productivity.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, I might say that the Karnataka cotton ginning business faculty, satisfied with all of the government help estimates provided during the project, but ultimately had a few claims. It important to appropriately communicate representative Favors and additional government support allocations in an, order to foster the faculty's inspiration and trust. Government aid centres can excite and retain workers. This may even help the representatives remain steadfast and dependable to the organization. Workers who have been aroused by the usage of government aid measures often find government assistance offices to be a sterile manner.

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